

CAPI, Flávio. **Jardim Atlântico**. São Paulo: SESI-SP, 2017.

REVIEW¹

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Flávio Capi builds this album by qualifying it as a movie-book, with visual characteristics that markedly lead us to the cinematic language. Delicate and watercolor images set the plot in the future, in the year 2082, in a small space of ecocultural preservation, in an ultra-urban area. Harmonic images keep the reader's attention with a suggestive visual narrative.

Keywords: Cinema. Images. Cine-book.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2018 Bologna. Books published in 2017 and reviewed in 2018. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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